

INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF OPERATOR COMPANIES IN THE TRANSPORT MARKET IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236937>

Abstract

In the modern digital era, the transportation industry is undergoing transformational changes caused by rapid technological advances and changes in consumer expectations. Operators, which play a key role in this sector, are forced to adapt to these changes in order to remain competitive. In this paper, along with the principles of modeling based on the author's economic-geographical method, Knoll's circle theory, originally developed by B. Knoll, is used to analyze and solve specific problems faced by operator companies. This theoretical framework helps to understand the interaction between various economic, technological and regulatory factors that affect the competitiveness of operator companies in the transportation market. The results of the research are variants of modeling the transport services market in terms of space (transport) efficiency built in software environments and the adaptation of Knoll's circle theory to the problems of operator companies.

Keywords: competitiveness, operator companies, transport market, digital economy, Knoll circles, modeling

In the dynamic landscape of the digital economy, transport operators face a dual imperative: evolve to meet changing market demands or risk obsolescence. The transition from traditional business models to those embracing digital innovation is pivotal for sustainable growth and competitiveness in the transport sector. This paper delves into the complexities that transport operators encounter in this digital milieu, highlighting both the opportunities for enhanced efficiency and the multifaceted challenges that accompany technological adoption.

The infusion of digital technologies in transport operations offers profound advantages. Advanced data analytics, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things (IoT) are revolutionizing how services are delivered, with significant improvements in operational efficiency and cost reduction. For example, predictive maintenance powered by AI can preempt equipment failures, minimizing downtime and extending asset life spans. Similarly, real-time data analytics enable more efficient route planning and asset tracking, enhancing service reliability and customer satisfaction.

However, the rapid pace of digital transformation also introduces significant challenges. Increased competition is a direct consequence as market entry barriers lower, enabling new players to disrupt established norms. Traditional transport operators must rapidly adapt to retain their market share, necessitating continuous technological upgrades and innovations. Furthermore, the digital economy demands a shift in organizational culture and skillsets, with a greater emphasis on digital literacy and data-driven decision-making.

The central objective of this article is to explore and articulate the primary challenges and strategic measures essential for enhancing the competitiveness of operator companies within the dynamic and digitally

evolving transport market. The analysis is grounded in both internal and external factors: the integration of advanced technologies and improved operational efficiencies internally, and externally, the shifting customer expectations, competitive market evolution, and global technological trends. Utilizing B. Knoll's circle theory, this research provides a structured analysis of the prevailing obstacles transport operators face, alongside proposing actionable strategies aimed at bolstering their market standing.

The competitiveness of transport service companies is a multifaceted issue that is influenced by various factors, including market conditions, service quality, and strategic management. Research shows that understanding these dynamics is critical to improving the efficiency and sustainability of transport and logistics companies, especially in difficult conditions.

Key factors affecting competitiveness

Service quality: The quality of transport and logistics services is of paramount importance. Companies must adapt to the growing consumer demand for high-quality services while effectively managing costs [1].

Logistics efficiency: The efficiency of transport systems directly impacts trade facilitation and overall competitiveness. Countries with underdeveloped logistics systems incur higher indirect costs, which impacts their global trading position [3].

While the focus on improving competitiveness is essential, it is also important to recognize that some companies may find it difficult to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions, which may lead to a reduction in their competitive advantage. This highlights the need for continuous assessment and adaptation in the transport services sector.

In the paper [1], the authors emphasize that the competitiveness of transport companies is of crucial

importance, since it depends on the quality of the services offered. Understanding consumer needs and implementing effective marketing strategies are necessary to increase competitiveness in the transport services market.

The findings underscore the need for targeted public policies to improve logistics infrastructure and efficiency, particularly in customs and trade logistics, to increase global production. Additionally, the study highlights the potential for improving the logistics sector to support sustainable development and economic interdependence among countries. This research provides important insights for policymakers and managers, indicating that effective logistics management can drive substantial improvements in production efficiency and overall economic performance [2].

The paper [3] identifies significant differences in the efficiency of transport and logistics systems between countries, which affect their competitiveness. It emphasizes the need to improve transport systems to simplify trade procedures and reduce logistics costs, which are crucial for the competitiveness of operating companies.

The paper [4] examines the competitiveness of logistics companies in Russia, emphasizing the importance of analyzing internal and external conditions to strengthen their market positions, which makes this industry an important object of research in the field of transport logistics and economics.

The paper [6] emphasizes that the efficiency of freight transport significantly affects the competitiveness of international trade, emphasizes that efficient logistics factors increase the market competitiveness of operating companies, and geographical remoteness negatively affects trade, emphasizing the importance of efficient transport services in logistics and the economy.

The paper [7] highlights the role of logistics in enhancing national competitiveness and notes that

transport service companies play a key role in economic growth. It highlights the importance of logistics efficiency in enhancing competitiveness in various country groups, including the EU, BRICS and ASEAN.

The vicious cycle theory developed by B. Knull is used to understand the cyclical downturns experienced by companies. This theory is applicable to the transport sector, where cycles of underinvestment can lead to lower productivity, preventing modernization and integration of new technologies [4].

In [8], the author suggests that strategic investments and favorable conditions play a decisive role in breaking harmful cycles, thereby contributing to the growth of the industry.

In [9-14], the authors consider approaches to quantitative assessment of competitiveness using multi-criteria analysis and optimization models. These models assess not only the competitiveness of operating companies, but also logistics chains, taking into account various factors, such as technological infrastructure, tariff rates and the efficiency of multimodal systems in distributing car flows. This methodological approach is especially useful for operators in competitive markets, where a detailed understanding of numerous operational parameters is crucial for developing optimal strategies.

Operating companies that actively implement digital technologies have the opportunity to increase their competitiveness. For example, optimizing the distribution of empty wagon flows allows reducing the wagon mileage. According to data for the first quarter of 2023, there is a decrease in empty mileage to the total by 1.2% for all types of rolling stock compared to the same period in 2022 (Pic. 1). The percentage of empty mileage to loaded mileage decreased by 3.5% in the segment of all types of rolling stock, and by 0.4% in the gondola wagon segment (Pic. 2).

By members of SOJKT (weighted average)
 Pic. 1 Percentage of empty run to total run

By members of SOJKT (weighted average)
 Pic. 2 Percentage of empty mileage to loaded mileage

In the swiftly evolving digital economy, transport operators face a triad of challenges that intricately affect their ability to compete and thrive. These challenges span technological advancements, market dynamics, and institutional constraints, each interplaying to potentially spiral into a cycle of reduced competitiveness as conceptualized by B. Knull's theory [11] (Pic. 3). Understanding and addressing these challenges is paramount for operators to break free from this detrimental cycle and secure a sustainable competitive edge.

Technological Challenges. The technological landscape within the transport sector is characterized by rapid evolution. Operators are tasked with the integration of cutting-edge digital technologies, which are crucial for optimizing operations and enhancing service delivery. However, this comes with challenges such as:

Implementing New Technologies: Adopting technologies like AI, IoT, and blockchain requires significant capital investment and operational overhauling.

Fleet Renewal: Continuously updating the transport fleet to incorporate the latest in energy efficiency and automation technologies.

Cybersecurity Risks: As reliance on digital platforms increases, so does the vulnerability to cyber threats and the imperative for robust data protection measures.

Market dynamics present a set of challenges shaped by external consumer and economic forces:

Changing Demand Patterns: Operators must adapt to shifts in consumer behavior, such as the increasing

demand for on-demand and environmentally sustainable transport options.

Increased Competition: The lowering of market entry barriers through technology leads to heightened competition, not just from traditional competitors but also from tech-driven entrants.

Institutional factors also play a critical role in shaping the operational environment for transport operators:

Regulatory Barriers: Navigating a complex and often stringent regulatory landscape that can vary significantly by region and type of service.

Legal Framework Adjustments: Keeping pace with legal adjustments that govern the digital transformations in the transport sector.

Shortage of Skilled Personnel: The industry faces a growing need for skilled professionals who are adept in new technologies and innovative business practices.

Breaking the Cycle of Declining Competitiveness
 The interaction of these challenges can lead to a vicious cycle where diminishing competitiveness results in decreased revenues, thereby restricting the funds available for necessary investments in technology and skilled personnel. This can stunt innovation and further degrade the operator's market position. To counteract this cycle, targeted strategic interventions are needed:

Pic. 3 Knull's «Vicious Circle» describing the challenges of operator companies

Investment in Technology and Skills: Prioritizing investments in new technologies and workforce training can enhance operational efficiency and service quality.

Adaptive Market Strategies: Operators should focus on flexible business models that allow for quick adaptation to changing market conditions and consumer preferences.

Engagement with Regulatory Bodies: Actively engaging with policymakers can help shape a more favorable regulatory environment that supports innovation and growth.

By addressing each of these critical areas, transport operators can forge a path towards sustained competitiveness in the digital marketplace, leveraging their strengths to innovate, adapt, and ultimately flourish.

Increasing the competitiveness of operating companies is also possible with the use of mathematical methods. For example, the method of economic and geographical distribution of wagon flows of operating companies [15], which, taking into account the relevant specifics, can be used to find rational transportation schemes. Modeling options for the corresponding transport polygon are presented in Pic 4.

Pic. 4 Division of a part of a polygon into “areas of influence” of departure stations in duopolistic situations

The rapidly evolving digital landscape presents numerous challenges for transport operators, requiring deliberate and strategic interventions to maintain and enhance their competitive edge. Building on the insights derived from B. Knull's circle theory, this section outlines a multifaceted approach to breaking the cycle of competitive decline and fostering sustainable growth.

Digital transformation stands at the forefront of strategic imperatives for transport operators. Key initiatives should include.

Integration of Platform Solutions: Leveraging comprehensive digital platforms that unify operations, customer service, and back-office processes can streamline workflows and enhance service delivery.

Process Automation: Automating routine tasks and operations can significantly increase efficiency and reduce human error, freeing up resources to focus on more strategic activities.

Blockchain for Enhanced Security and Transparency: Implementing blockchain technology can revolutionize aspects of operations ranging from ticketing to supply chain management, offering unmatched transparency and improving security against fraud.

Infrastructure modernization is another critical area requiring attention and investment.

Incorporating smart technologies like IoT-enabled devices and AI can optimize asset management and predictive maintenance, leading to lower downtime and reduced operational costs.

Investing in modern, efficient, and environmentally friendly rolling stock is essential not only for reducing operational costs but also for meeting increasing regulatory and consumer demands for sustainability.

To effectively compete in a crowded market, operators must shift from price-based competition to differentiating their service offerings:

Offering Sustainable Options: Developing environmentally sustainable transport options resonates with the growing consumer demand for green services and can provide a competitive edge in markets increasingly driven by ecological concerns.

Conclusion

The application of B. Knull's circle theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex, interconnected challenges facing transport operators today. By addressing these challenges through a strategic, integrated approach—focusing on digital transformation, infrastructure modernization, service differentiation, and human resource support—operators can not only break the cycle of declining competitiveness but also position themselves robustly for future challenges and opportunities in the digital economy.

Acknowledgements

The research was supported by the Russian Science Foundation grant No. 24-29-00869, <https://rscf.ru/project/24-29-00869/>

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